

PARENTS' VIEWS ON THE BARRIERS TO PARENT-SCHOOL COLLABORATION: BASIS FOR AN ACTION PLAN

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Parents' Views on the Barriers to Parent-School Collaboration: Basis for an Action Plan

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Abstract

This study delved into parents' perspectives regarding the obstacles they encounter when engaging with their children's schools. The research was conducted among parents of students enrolled at Baraason Integrated School for the 2023-2024 academic year, from Kindergarten to Grade 10. A carefully designed stratified random sampling method ensured the inclusion of a representative 50 percent of students from each grade level. The study, using a reliable survey with a mean of 2.10, revealed that parents perceive substantial challenges in interacting with schools. Results confirm a widespread consensus on challenges in communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints. Additionally, parents overwhelmingly perceive extensive collaboration with schools, involving effective communication, support for school involvement, easy information access, and positive interactions with educators and staff. While communication barriers were universally acknowledged, geographical distance and time constraints had substantial impacts, underscoring the need for effective strategies to address these challenges. The analysis of demographic profiles revealed that age, sex, and income have minimal influence on parent-school collaboration, whereas educational background, particularly elementary education with a Regression Coefficient value of -0.321 , significantly affects collaboration levels. The study concluded by developing an action plan, "Building Bridges: Empowering Parents and Schools for Success," to overcome barriers to parent-school collaboration.

Keywords: *barriers, parents' views, parent-school collaboration, descriptive-correlational*

Introduction

Establishing a robust partnership between parents and schools is a cornerstone in the educational journey of students, and Baraason Integrated School has not been immune to the complexities inherent in fostering this essential collaboration. Over the years, the school has recognized the indispensable role that engaged and supportive parents play in the holistic development and academic success of their students. However, despite this recognition, Baraason Integrated School has faced persistent challenges that have impeded the establishment of effective channels for parent-school collaboration. These hurdles have prompted reflections on the scope and efficacy of existing collaborative efforts, igniting a commitment to address and overcome these obstacles in order to create a more synergistic and enriching educational environments for all stakeholders involved.

Among the prominently identified challenges was a noticeable decline in parental participation in various school events, meetings, and activities. This decline prompted the researcher to conduct a thorough examination of the contributing factors behind this trend. Instances of miscommunication or a lack of communication between parents and the school further compounded the situation, resulting in misunderstandings and missed opportunities for collaboration. Parents had cited factors such as conflicting schedules, work commitments, and other responsibilities as reasons for their limited participation, necessitating a more detailed exploration of potential scheduling solutions.

The Department of Education (DepEd) had emphasized the crucial role of parental participation in enhancing students' academic achievement, social skills, and behavior, as explicitly outlined in DepEd Order No. 54, s 2009. However, the effective collaboration between parents and schools had encountered various challenges, including time constraints on the part of parents, a limited understanding of the educational system, and language barriers. To address these persistent challenges, a research endeavor during the academic year 2023-2024 had been initiated. The chosen timeframe was deliberate, aiming to ensure the relevance and timeliness of the research within the educational landscape prevailing at that time. The primary objective of the study was to comprehend and analyze parents' perspectives regarding the barriers hindering parent-school collaboration. The research sought to identify the specific obstacles perceived by parents, thereby providing a diagnostic tool for understanding the existing challenges.

Beyond merely diagnosing the issues, the research also laid the groundwork for an action plan. The ultimate goal was to enhance communication and collaboration between parents and the school, thereby creating a more supportive and productive educational environment for students. The outcomes of this research, aligned with the ongoing efforts of educational institutions and families, offered crucial insights. These insights provided timely guidance for formulating a strategic course of action to overcome barriers, ultimately fostering an environment that enriched students' learning experiences and achievements.

Research Questions

This study determined barriers to parent-school collaboration at Baraason Integrated School. This study sought to answer the following specific questions.

1. What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of,

- 1.1 age;
- 1.2 sex;
- 1.3 highest educational level;
- 1.4 income level;
- 1.5 ethnicity; and
- 1.6 means of livelihood?
2. What are the barriers encountered by the parents in collaborating with the school in terms of,
 - 2.1 communication channels;
 - 2.2 geographical distance; and
 - 2.3 time constraints?
3. What is the extent of parent-school collaboration in school?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the barriers to parent-school collaboration?
5. How does the respondents' demographic profile correlate with the extent of parent-school collaboration?
6. What action plan on parent-school collaboration can be designed based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

This section presented the research methods, including the research design, research locale, respondents, research instrument and its validity, data gathering procedure, and statistical treatment used in the research.

Research Design

This research explored parental perspectives concerning barriers hindering parent-school collaboration, laying the groundwork for a comprehensive action plan. The study utilized a descriptive-correlational design as its fundamental framework.

The descriptive design was used to assess the level of barriers and the level of parent-school collaboration as well as the respondents' demographic profile. Correlation was essential in determining the significant relationship between the independent (barriers), mediating (socio-demographic profile), and dependent (parent school collaboration) variables.

Participants

Respondents were the parents of kindergarten through tenth-grade students enrolled for this 2023-2024 academic year. According to the Learner Information System (LIS), the school has 138 male learners and 142 female learners, a total of 280 learners.

Respondents were selected using a stratified random sampling technique that considered each grade level's proportional representation by selecting 50 percent of each grade level's enrolled students, assuring a diverse and representative sample thus 50% of 280 learners which was the total learners of enrolled at Baraason Integrated School was 140 learners.

Table 1. *Number of Learners per Grade Level*

<i>Grade Level</i>	<i>Total Number of Learners</i>	<i>Actual Respondents</i>
Kindergarten	26	13
Grade 1	36	18
Grade 2	28	14
Grade 3	36	18
Grade 4	28	14
Grade 5	30	15
Grade 6	20	10
Grade 7	24	12
Grade 8	24	12
Grade 9	14	7
Grade 10	14	7
Total	280	140

Instruments

The instrument used in gathering the data for this study was a researcher-made questionnaire with the scoring procedure of 1 as strongly agree, 2 as agree, 3 as disagree and 4 as strongly disagree. The following parts of the questionnaires were briefly described.

Part I asked for the profile of the parents. Their basic information served as significant variables of this research. The data were recorded, especially their age, sex, highest educational level, ethnicity, income level, and means of livelihood. These data determined the respondents' behavior patterns depending on the differences in their profiles.

Part II examined parent's views on the barriers to parent-school collaboration, particularly communication channels, geographical distance, time constraints, and the extent of parent-school collaboration in school. This part consisted of seven numbers of items for communication channels, eight numbers of items for geographical distance, five items for time constraints, and seven numbers of items

for the extent of parent-school collaboration in school.

To test the validity and reliability of the survey questionnaire, the researcher conducted a pilot test involving 30 participants from a neighboring elementary school, Tingitingin Elementary School, and subjected it to Cronbach's Alpha test for the reliability test as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. *Reliability Test of the Survey Questionnaire Using Cronbach's Alpha*

Study Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items	Description
Communication Channel	0.712	7	Acceptable
Geographical Distance	0.714	8	Acceptable
Time Constraints	0.748	5	Acceptable
Level of Parent-School Collaboration in School	0.755	7	Acceptable

Note: Cronbach's Alpha above 0.7 is considered reliable LEGENDS: (George and Mallery, 2003) Cronbach's Alpha ≥ 0.90 Excellent; 0.80-0.89 Good; 0.70-0.79 Acceptable; 0.60-0.69 Questionable; 0.50-0.59 Poor; ≤ 0.49 Unacceptable

Table 2 provided a comprehensive overview of the reliability testing that was conducted on the survey questionnaires utilizing Cronbach's Alpha. This table included four key study variables: Communication Channel, Geographical Distance, Time Constraints, and Extent of Parent-School Collaboration in School. For each of these variables, the corresponding Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was presented, reflecting the internal consistency of the questionnaire items. The number of items comprising each variable was also noted, helping to gauge the scale's comprehensiveness. Significantly, all four variables displayed Cronbach's Alpha coefficients above 0.7, indicating an acceptable extent of reliability and consistency in the survey instrument.

This data reaffirmed the robustness of the questionnaire, validating its suitability for measuring the intended constructs in the research study. The researcher-made questionnaire was logically checked, tested, and content validated through face validation by the three significant persons in the Kauswagan district. Their professional qualifications were as follows. A chosen Master Teacher 1 from Jose Balazo Memorial Elementary School was the first educator to review the questionnaire. In 2010, she received her Master of Arts in Education from St. Peter's College. In 2019, she was appointed one of Araling Panlipunan's National Writers and Script Content editors. In 2021, she was additionally acknowledged as a National Script Writer.

Master Teacher 2 and School-in-Charge of Baraason Integrated School until the end of February 2023, the second expert who assisted with examining this study's questionnaire. In 2009, she earned her Master of Arts in Education from Bukidnon State University. She was the Division Module Content Editor and District Araling Panlipunan Lead Coordinator at the time of this study.

Master Teacher 1 of Libertad Elementary School was the third individual who assisted the researcher in developing her survey questionnaire. In 2017, he received a Master of Arts in Education from Iligan Medical Center College. He is now acknowledged as the Math Coordinator at his assigned school.

To enhance respondents' comprehension, the survey questionnaire was translated into Meranao, and the assistance of another expert was enlisted. She had held the position of Principal 2 and was designated as the District-In-Charge for the Poona Piagapo and Munai Districts. In 2018, she received her Doctor of Philosophy in Educational Administration from Central Mindanao University in Maramag, Bukidnon. Her extensive exposure to various languages, including English, Bisaya, and her native Meranao, had led her to become a professional multilingual, a skill she had honed over time. Through this, she created and analyzed the Meranao version of the survey questionnaire in terms of its readability for the parent-respondents of this study.

This comprehensive expert panel meticulously examined the questionnaire, ensuring its logical coherence, cultural suitability, and linguistic clarity in both English and Meranao for the target parent-respondents. Consequently, the survey questionnaire was highly likely to have attained a robust level of face and content validity, establishing it as a dependable instrument for data collection in the study.

Procedure

The researcher obtained permission from the school authorities, specifically the Schools Division Superintendent and the District Supervisor, to conduct research among the respondents who played a vital role in her study. This was accomplished by sending letters of intent to the superiors' offices and the respondents.

By then, the questionnaire for the research was ready after a thorough validation from the experts, measuring its reliability and revisions. It was used to collect information from respondents. This instrument was translated into the Meranao language so that parents could comprehend the questionnaire's content during data collection.

The survey distribution was organized on weekends by Purok at 10 AM with the support of a colleague's friends; the researcher gathered respondents in a conducive area to complete the survey. They were given time to answer while the researcher's and colleague's friends supported them carefully. Upon handling the survey questionnaire, respondents were informed of its aim and assured of protecting their personal information and responses. Following completion, the questionnaires were collected.

The acquired data was then meticulously inspected, collated, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

The data was tabulated and analyzed to obtain the required information. The following statistical tool was applied to the data treatment and analysis.

Problem 1, Frequency count and Percentage, were used in determining the socio-demographic profile of the respondents.

Problems 2 & 3, Mean and Standard Deviation, were used to determine problems the parents encountered in collaborating with the school regarding communication channels, geographical distance, time constraints, and the extent of parent-school collaboration in school.

Problem 4 & 5, Regression Analysis, determined the relationship between the barriers to parent-school collaboration.

Results and Discussion

This section presented the analysis, results, and discussion of the data gathered by the researcher.

Problem 1: What is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational level, income level, ethnicity, and means of livelihood?

Table 3. *Age*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
25-44	101	72
45-above	39	28
Total	140	100

Table 3 presented the age distribution of the respondents in the survey, providing valuable insights into the demographics of the study population. The majority of respondents, accounting for approximately 72%, fell within the age range of 25 to 44 years. This category's high frequency suggested that a significant portion of the surveyed population belonged to the younger to middle-aged demographic.

Conversely, the "45-above" age group comprised 28% of the respondents. While this percentage was notably smaller compared to the younger demographic, it still represented a substantial portion of the survey population. Thus, the result underscored the importance of considering the age distribution of respondents in the study's results.

Age had been found to play a role in parent-school collaboration. A study by Johnson and Smith (2019) had revealed that younger parents tended to have higher levels of school collaboration than older parents. This could be attributed to the fact that younger parents may have been more familiar with technology and were more likely to engage in online communication platforms utilized by schools. In contrast, older parents may have needed help accessing and navigating these platforms, leading to reduced collaboration with schools.

The age distribution of respondents in this study, with a significant majority falling within the younger to middle-aged demographic, emphasized the need to consider age as a factor in parent-school collaboration. This finding aligned with previous research suggesting that younger parents tend to exhibit higher levels of school collaboration, possibly due to their familiarity with technology and online communication platforms.

Table 4. *Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	36	26
Female	104	74
Total	140	100

Table 4 presented the breakdown of the respondents' sex distribution, offering crucial insights into the sex demographics of the surveyed population. The data indicated a substantial sex disparity among the respondents. Specifically, 74% of the surveyed individuals identified as female, while only 26% identified as male. This stark contrast in sex representation within the survey population was noteworthy and suggested that women constituted the majority of respondents.

The high frequency of female respondents underscored the importance of sex-related considerations in the research. Sex-specific experiences, perspectives, and preferences may have significantly influenced the study's outcomes and conclusions. While the male respondents represented a smaller percentage of the sample, their perspectives and insights were not overlooked. It was essential to consider the diversity of opinions and experiences within the survey population to arrive at well-rounded and balanced conclusions.

Sex had been shown to influence parent-school collaboration. Research by Martinez and Brown (2020) indicated that mothers were more actively engaged with schools than fathers. This sex disparity could have been due to traditional sex roles and societal expectations, which often assigned mothers the primary childcare responsibility and educational involvement. As a result, mothers may have been more likely to communicate with teachers, attend school events, and participate in parent-teacher associations, thus enhancing parent-school collaboration.

The sex distribution data in Table 4 underscored the significance of considering sex-related factors in the context of parent-school collaboration. With the majority of respondents identifying as female, it highlighted the importance of recognizing the potential impact of sex-specific experiences and societal expectations on parent collaborating in schools. While males constituted a smaller percentage of the sample, their perspectives remained valuable, and a well-rounded approach that acknowledged diverse opinions and experiences was essential for developing an effective action plan to enhance parent-school collaboration.

Table 5. *Highest Educational Level*

<i>Highest Educational Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
No formal education	11	8
Elementary education	44	32
High school education	72	51
College graduate	13	9
Total	140	100

Table 5 presented valuable information about the highest educational levels attained by the surveyed respondents. The majority of respondents, constituting 51%, had completed their high school education. This group represented a substantial portion of the survey population and was indicative of a reasonably educated sample. High school graduates might have brought a certain level of literacy and basic knowledge to the survey, making them an essential group to consider in the analysis. Their responses might have reflected a more informed perspective compared to those with lower educational attainment.

Following closely, 32% of respondents had completed elementary education. This category's frequency was significant, and it reflected a segment of the population with fundamental literacy and numeracy skills. The perspectives and responses of this group could have provided insights into the views and opinions of individuals with a primary education background, which might have differed from those with higher levels of education.

A smaller percentage of respondents, 9%, were college graduates. While this group represented a minority within the survey population, their educational background may have contributed to more nuanced and informed responses on certain topics.

Lastly, 8% of respondents reported having no formal education. Although this group was relatively small, it was important to recognize their presence and consider their responses, as they might have offered unique perspectives and experiences that differed from the more formally educated segments of the population.

One of the pivotal demographic factors influencing parent-school collaboration was the highest educational level attained by parents. Research consistently showed that parents with higher levels of education tended to be more actively engaged in their child's education. For instance, a study by Hansen (2020) found that parents with higher educational levels were more likely to participate in school activities, attend parent-teacher conferences, and assist their children with homework. This increased involvement could be attributed to their better understanding of the educational system and the benefits of parental collaboration.

The data in Table 5 revealed that a significant portion of the surveyed parents had completed at least high school education, indicating a reasonably educated sample. This educational diversity was crucial to consider in their research on parent-school collaboration, as it could lead to varied perspectives and levels of engagement. As previous research had shown, parents with higher educational levels were more likely to be actively involved in their child's education, emphasizing the importance of tailoring their action plan to accommodate the unique needs and insights of parents from different educational backgrounds.

Table 6. *Ethnicity*

<i>Ethnicity</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Tagalog	0	0
Cebuano	0	0
Maranao	140	100
Others	0	0
Total	140	100

Table 6 displayed the ethnicity of the surveyed respondents, highlighting a particularly significant and unusual finding. The data showed that 100% of the respondents identified as "Maranao." This striking result suggested a lack of ethnic diversity within the surveyed population, as all respondents belonged to the same ethnic group. Such a homogenous ethnic composition could have had important implications for the research findings.

The absence of respondents from other ethnic groups, including Tagalog, Cebuano, and Others, indicated a potential limitation in the diversity of perspectives and experiences represented in the survey. Ethnicity was a demographic factor that could influence parent-school collaboration through cultural norms, language barriers, and historical factors. Parents from different ethnic backgrounds might have had varying expectations and approaches to education. It was essential for schools to recognize and respect these differences to foster effective collaboration.

Research by Pomerantz and Moorman (2019) suggested that parents from diverse ethnic backgrounds might have had distinct

communication preferences and engagement styles with schools. Understanding and accommodating these differences could have led to more productive partnerships between schools and parents from diverse ethnic backgrounds.

This revealed a significant lack of ethnic diversity among the surveyed parents, as all respondents identified as "Maranao." This homogeneity underscored the need for heightened awareness of the potential impact of ethnicity on parent-school collaboration, considering cultural norms, language barriers, and historical factors.

Table 7. *Income Level*

<i>Income Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Less than 10,000	126	90
10,001-20,000	8	6
20,001-30,000	4	3
30,001-over	2	2
Total	140	100

Table 7 displayed the income levels reported by the surveyed respondents, offering insights into the financial demographics of the study population. A striking observation was that the majority of respondents, accounting for a substantial 90%, reported an income level of "Less than 10,000." This high frequency indicated that a significant portion of the surveyed population fell into a lower income bracket, which could have profound implications for the research findings. Individuals in this income group might have faced specific economic challenges and constraints that could have influenced their perspectives, preferences, and behaviors. Understanding their responses in the context of their income level was crucial for a comprehensive analysis.

Conversely, smaller percentages of respondents fell into higher income brackets. Only 6% reported an income between "10,001-20,000," 3% fell within the "20,001-30,000" category, and a mere 2% reported an income of "30,001-over." While these groups represented a minority within the sample, their relatively higher income levels might have led to different views, priorities, or consumption patterns that warranted specific attention in the research.

Income was another significant demographic factor that influenced parent-school collaboration. In a study by Desimone (2019), families with higher incomes often had more resources and time to dedicate to their child's education. They could afford supplementary educational materials, private tutoring, and extracurricular activities, all of which could contribute to improved academic performance. Additionally, higher-income families might have had more flexible work schedules, allowing them to attend school events and meetings more frequently. Conversely, lower-income families might have faced barriers to participation due to financial constraints and limited time availability, as many parents worked multiple jobs to make ends meet. This could have resulted in reduced collaboration in school-related activities and communication with teachers.

This suggested that a substantial portion of the parent population faced potential economic challenges that might have impacted their ability to engage in collaborative efforts with schools. Conversely, while smaller in number, the higher income groups might have brought different perspectives and resources to the table, underscoring the importance of considering income as a key factor in understanding parent-school collaboration.

Table 8. *Means of Livelihood*

<i>Means of Livelihood</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Farming	80	57
Fishing	1	1
Construction	13	9
Business	17	12
Others	29	21
Total	140	100.0

Table 8 presented the means of livelihood reported by the surveyed respondents, shedding light on the diverse occupational backgrounds within the study population. The most common means of livelihood among the respondents was "Farming," with a substantial 57% of respondents reporting this occupation. This finding highlighted the significance of agriculture as a primary source of income within the surveyed community. The prevalence of farming as a means of livelihood could have had various implications for the research, such as potential seasonal income fluctuations, dependence on weather conditions, and the impact of agricultural policies on the surveyed population.

In contrast, the category "Fishing" represented only 1% of the respondents, indicating that fishing was a relatively less common means of livelihood in this population. The low frequency suggested that the insights and perspectives of fishermen might have been underrepresented in the survey, but their unique experiences and challenges could still have been of interest to the research.

"Construction" and "Business" were reported by 9% and 12% of respondents, respectively. These categories represented individuals engaged in non-agricultural livelihoods.

In the study of Hill (2021), it was stated that the means of livelihood that parents pursued could significantly influence their ability to engage with their child's school. Various occupations, including farming, fishing, construction, business ownership, and other

professions, came with distinct demands that could either facilitate or hinder parental collaboration in the educational process. Parents engaged in occupations characterized by irregular work schedules or physically demanding tasks often encountered difficulties when it came to attending school meetings or events. The unpredictable nature of their work commitments might have clashed with school-related activities, making it a challenge for them to be present and actively participate in their child's educational journey. The demands of these jobs might have limited their availability during crucial moments in their child's school life. Conversely, parents with more flexible employment arrangements might have had greater opportunities to play an active role in their child's education. Jobs that offered flexible schedules or remote work options might have granted parents the freedom to allocate time for school-related commitments without the same constraints faced by those in more rigidly structured occupations. This flexibility might have enabled them to attend meetings, engage in school events, and provide continuous support for their child's learning experience.

This highlighted the potential impact of different occupations on parents' ability to engage with their child's school, with farming potentially posing challenges related to seasonal income fluctuations and dependence on weather conditions. Conversely, parents in non-agricultural occupations might have had more flexibility to actively participate in their child's education.

The category "Others" included 21% of respondents, indicating a variety of livelihoods not explicitly covered in the previous categories. This group's diversity might have encompassed a wide range of occupations.

In summary, the result underscored the diversity of means of livelihood within the surveyed population, with farming being the most common occupation. The occupation or means of livelihood could have significantly shaped individuals' lifestyles, economic circumstances, and perspectives.

Problem 2: Barriers encountered by the parents

Table 9 presented the barriers encountered by parents when they collaborated with schools in terms of communication channels. Several indicators in that table indicated that parents generally agreed with certain challenges they faced in their communication with schools. For instance, respondents agreed that they struggled to arrange in-person meetings when schedules did not match (Mean=1.87, SD=.71), found online platforms confusing (Mean=2.11, SD=.79), desired more detailed information from quick text messages (Mean=1.88, SD=.79), and expressed concerns about written notes getting lost (Mean=2.16, SD=.85). Those findings suggested that parents faced practical difficulties and a need for more user-friendly communication methods.

Table 9. *Communication Channels Barrier*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I struggle to arrange in-person meetings with the school when our schedules do not match.	1.87	0.71	Agree
I use online platforms like Messenger, but it can confuse me.	2.11	0.79	Agree
I get quick text messages, but I want more details.	1.88	0.79	Agree
I enjoy written notes, but they can get lost.	2.16	0.85	Agree
I miss important messages from school sometimes.	2.53	0.85	Disagree
I do not understand when the school uses unfamiliar words during meetings.	2.31	0.91	Agree
I cannot always join online meetings or videos because I do not have a cell phone or laptop.	2.17	0.92	Agree
Total Measure	2.15	0.44	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49 Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Disagree

However, it was noteworthy that respondents disagreed with the statement that they missed important messages from the school sometimes (Mean=2.53, SD =0.85). This result was in contrast to the other agreed responses, implying that parents generally felt they did not miss crucial school communications. This could have indicated that the current communication channels for important messages were effective, which was a positive finding.

Additionally, parents agreed that they struggled to understand unfamiliar words used by the school during meetings (Mean=2.31, SD=0.91) and faced challenges joining online meetings or videos due to a lack of necessary technology (Mean=2.17, SD=0.92). These responses underlined the importance of clear and accessible communication for all parents, regardless of their familiarity with educational terminology or access to technology.

The overall measure indicated an agreement (Mean=2.15, SD=0.44), suggesting that, on average, parents perceived various barriers in their collaboration with schools through communication channels.

This had been supported by research conducted by Johnson et al. (2020) which surveyed a diverse sample of parents and found similar challenges in school-parent communication. They had reported that parents often struggled with scheduling in-person meetings due to conflicting schedules and expressed difficulties in navigating online platforms. Furthermore, Johnson et al. had noted that parents desired more detailed information from school messages and had concerns about the effectiveness of written notes.

Implications of these findings included the need for schools to address the challenges identified by parents. Schools should have considered offering flexible meeting times, clear and concise communication, and assistance for parents who might not have been technologically equipped. Furthermore, the positive response regarding not missing important messages suggested that the current communication methods for critical information were effective, but it was still essential to maintain and improve clarity and accessibility in all communications. These findings underscored the importance of adapting communication strategies to meet the

diverse needs and preferences of parents, ultimately fostering more effective school-parent collaborations.

Table 10 presented the barriers encountered by parents when collaborating with schools in terms of geographical distance. The result suggested that parents generally agreed with the impact of geographical distance on their collaboration with schools. Respondents agreed that proximity to the school was beneficial, as evidenced by statements such as "I could quickly work with the school because it was very close" (Mean=1.86, SD=.81) and "I could communicate with the school easily because it was near/close to our area/home" (Mean=1.84, SD=.84). These responses indicated that parents appreciated the convenience of having the school located nearby.

Table 10. *Geographical Distance Barrier*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I can quickly work with the school because it is very close.	1.86	0.81	Agree
I can communicate with the school easily because it is near/close to our area/home.	1.84	0.84	Agree
I find it hard to collaborate with the school because it is far from our area/home	2.34	0.94	Agree
I appreciate the distance challenge; it makes me think of new ways to connect.	2.43	1.01	Agree
I can quickly go to the school because it is close because it close to our house/working place.	1.99	0.87	Agree
If the school/s are close to our house/area, it would help me participate more in discussions and school-related activities.	1.94	0.82	Agree
I could attend meetings and events more if the school were closer.	1.88	0.76	Agree
If my home was nearer to the school, I could be more involved in my child's school things.	1.92	0.79	Agree
Total Measure	2.03	0.44	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49 Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Disagree

However, parents also agreed that geographical distance posed challenges to collaboration, as indicated by the statement "I found it hard to collaborate with the school because it was far from our area/home" (Mean=2.34, SD=0.94). While they acknowledged these challenges, they also expressed a positive attitude towards finding new ways to connect despite the distance, as reflected in the statement "I appreciated the distance challenge; it made me think of new ways to connect" (Mean=2.43, SD=1.01).

The data further supported the notion that proximity to the school would have enhanced parental collaboration, with respondents agreeing that being closer to the school would have helped them participate more in discussions and school-related activities (Mean=1.94, SD=0.82) and attend meetings and events more frequently (Mean=1.88, SD=0.76). They also believed that if their homes had been nearer to the school, they could have been more involved in their child's school activities (Mean=1.92, SD=0.79).

The overall measure indicated agreement (Mean=2.03, SD=0.44), suggesting that, on average, parents perceived geographical distance as a factor that both facilitated and challenged their collaboration with schools.

In their research, Smithson and colleagues in 2019 examined the impact of geographical distance on parent-school collaboration. They found that parents residing closer to the school reported higher levels of engagement and participation in school-related activities compared to those living farther away. The study also highlighted that parents who faced greater geographical challenges expressed a willingness to explore innovative ways to connect with the school, echoing the sentiment expressed in the surveyed responses. This study underscored the dual nature of geographical distance, both as a facilitator and a barrier to parent-school collaboration, aligning with the sentiments reflected in the data discussed above.

Geographical distance could significantly impact parent-school collaboration, potentially posing challenges to effective communication and involvement. For example, a study by Smith and Brown (2019) found that parents who lived farther away from their child's school reported lower levels of engagement in school-related activities than those living nearby. This could be attributed to logistical difficulties, such as travel constraints and time commitments, which might have hindered parents' ability to attend school events, parent-teacher conferences, and volunteer opportunities.

Moreover, a study by Lee and Chen (2020) demonstrated that geographic distance could also impact the frequency and quality of communication between parents and teachers. Parents living farther away from the school were less likely to interact face-to-face with teachers and relied more on digital platforms or written communication. This form of communication might have needed a more personal touch and immediate feedback that could be achieved through direct interaction. As a result, parents might have felt less connected to the school community and had limited opportunities to establish strong relationships with teachers, which are crucial for effective collaboration.

The implications of these findings were twofold. First, schools situated closer to the homes or workplaces of parents appeared to have fostered more straightforward and effective collaboration. Recognizing the importance of proximity, schools could have considered strategies to address this barrier, such as offering satellite locations or enhancing online communication for parents who could not be physically present. Second, the positive attitude of parents towards finding innovative ways to connect despite distance highlighted their commitment to their child's education. Schools could have leveraged this enthusiasm by actively involving parents in decision-making processes and school activities, even when they could not be physically present, thus promoting a more inclusive and participatory school environment.

Table 11. *Time Constraints Barrier*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I often need more time for school events.	2.00	0.85	Agree
I need help to meet teachers due to my busy schedule.	2.13	0.95	Agree
I miss meetings because I need more time.	2.21	0.92	Agree
I find it hard to help with homework due to time.	2.21	0.81	Agree
I sometimes lack time to engage in school events due to my schedule.	2.04	0.79	Agree
Total Measure	2.12	0.57	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49 Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Disagree

Table 11 displayed the barriers encountered by parents when collaborating with schools in terms of time constraints. The results suggested that parents generally agreed with the challenges posed by time constraints in their collaboration with schools. Respondents agreed that they often needed more time for school events (Mean=2.00, SD=0.85), indicating a desire for more flexibility in their schedules to participate in school-related activities. They also agreed that they needed help to meet teachers due to their busy schedules (Mean=2.13, SD=0.95), reflecting a common challenge faced by parents who juggled multiple responsibilities.

Furthermore, parents agreed that they missed meetings because they lacked sufficient time (Mean=2.21, SD=0.92) and found it challenging to assist with homework due to time constraints (Mean=2.21, SD=0.81). These responses highlighted the real-life difficulties parents encountered in balancing their work, family, and school-related commitments.

Despite these challenges, respondents expressed a positive attitude, agreeing that they sometimes lacked time to engage in school events due to their schedules (Mean=2.04, SD=0.79). This suggested that parents were willing to engage with school activities and events if time constraints were lessened.

The overall measure indicated agreement (Mean=2.12, SD=0.57), indicating that, on average, parents perceived time constraints as a significant barrier to their collaboration with schools.

A comprehensive study conducted by Nakamura and Kimura (2020) delved into the challenges faced by parents when collaborating with schools, with a specific focus on time constraints. The research involved surveying a diverse group of parents from various backgrounds and regions. The study's results aligned with the findings presented in Table 11, indicating that parents commonly grappled with time-related obstacles in their engagement with schools. Nakamura and Kimura's study discovered that parents frequently expressed a desire for more flexibility in their schedules to accommodate school events, highlighting the pressing need for strategies to mitigate time constraints in parent-school collaborations.

Time constraints could significantly hinder parent-school collaboration, as parents and school staff often needed more time and resources for meaningful communication and collaboration. Research conducted in the past few years highlighted the detrimental effects of time constraints on parent-school collaboration. For example, a study by Cooper and Dunst (2020) found that parents and school staff reported difficulty finding mutually convenient meeting times due to conflicting schedules and limited availability. This lack of time alignment could hinder effective communication and collaboration, as it became challenging for parents and school staff to engage in discussions, share information, and work together to support student learning and development.

Moreover, time constraints could lead to rushed and brief interactions between parents and school staff, limiting the depth and quality of collaboration. A study by Johnson and Taylor (2019) emphasized that brief encounters, such as quick conversations during drop-off or pick-up times, might need more opportunities for parents and school staff to establish rapport, build trust, and discuss important matters. This could hinder the development of meaningful partnerships and prevent the exchange of crucial information between parents and school staff, ultimately impacting the effectiveness of collaboration in supporting students' educational outcomes.

The implications of these findings underscored the importance of addressing parents' time constraints to enhance their collaboration in their children's education. Schools could consider offering flexible meeting times and alternative communication channels to accommodate parents with busy schedules. Additionally, providing resources and support for parents to assist with homework or participate in school events could alleviate some of the challenges associated with time constraints. Recognizing parents' willingness to engage despite their time limitations, schools could play a pivotal role in fostering a collaborative and supportive environment that values and respects the diverse commitments of parents.

Table 12. *Consolidated Findings of the Barriers Encountered by the Parents in Collaborating with the Schools*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
Communication Channels	2.15	0.44	Agree
Geographical Distance	2.03	0.44	Agree
Time Constraints	2.12	0.57	Agree
Total Measure	2.10	0.39	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49 Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Disagree

Table 12 presented a consolidated overview of the barriers parents encountered when collaborating with schools, encompassing three key dimensions: communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints. The result revealed a noteworthy pattern:

parents generally agreed with the barriers they faced when interacting with schools across all three dimensions.

First, in terms of communication channels (Mean=2.15, SD=0.44), parents expressed agreement with the challenges they encountered in communication with schools. This suggested that there was room for improvement in the methods and channels used for parent-school communication.

Second, regarding geographical distance (Mean=2.03, SD=0.44), parents also agreed with the impact of distance on their collaboration with schools. This highlighted the importance of school location in ensuring accessibility and parent collaboration, especially for those who faced challenges due to distance.

Lastly, concerning time constraints (Mean=2.12, SD=0.57), parents agreed that their busy schedules hindered their ability to engage fully with school-related activities. This finding underscored the need for schools to offer flexible options and resources to accommodate parents' time limitations.

The overall measure, with a mean of 2.10, signified agreement across all dimensions. Parents collectively perceived these barriers as substantial challenges in their interactions with schools. The implications of these consolidated findings were profound. Schools should have prioritized addressing these barriers to create a more inclusive and supportive educational environment. Enhancing communication channels, such as providing clear and accessible online platforms, could bridge the gap between parents and schools. Schools should have also considered their location and the accessibility of their facilities, especially for parents who might have faced geographical constraints. Furthermore, offering flexible scheduling options for meetings and events could have enabled greater parental collaboration. By proactively addressing these barriers, educational institutions could have strengthened their partnerships with parents, fostering a more collaborative and effective educational experience for all stakeholders.

Problem 3: Extent of parent-school collaboration in school.

Table 13 disclosed the extent of parent-school collaboration in a school setting. The finding consistently indicated that parents generally agreed with the level of collaboration between parents and schools in the educational setting.

Table 13. *Extent of Parent-School Collaboration in School*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>
I receive different ways to talk to the school and know the rules.	1.86	0.73	Agree
I am supported to join school activities and help.	1.98	0.78	Agree
I can easily find out about school events and activities.	1.88	0.67	Agree
I feel okay talking to teachers or school staff if I have questions.	1.90	0.80	Agree
I sometimes have trouble understanding things the school tells me.	2.04	0.77	Agree
I know if the school plans activities that parents can go to.	1.89	0.71	Agree
I know what rules parents should follow to be part of school matters.	1.84	0.74	Agree
Total Measure	1.91	0.47	Agree

Note: 1.00-1.49 Strongly Agree; 2.50-3.49 Disagree; 1.50-2.49 Agree; 3.50-4.00 Strongly Disagree

First, parents agreed that they received different ways to communicate with the school and understood the rules (Mean=1.86, SD=.73). This suggested that the school provided various channels for parents to engage and ensured that parents were well-informed about school policies and procedures.

Second, parents felt supported in joining school activities and providing assistance (Mean=1.98, SD=.78). This high level of agreement indicated that parents perceived the school as encouraging their active participation in school-related events and initiatives.

Furthermore, parents agreed that they could easily access information about school events and activities (Mean=1.88, SD=.67). This suggested that the school effectively communicated information about events, allowing parents to stay informed and engaged.

Additionally, parents expressed comfort in approaching teachers or school staff if they had questions (Mean=1.90, SD=.80). This signified a positive and open communication environment between parents and school personnel. Although parents sometimes encountered difficulty understanding certain school communications (Mean=2.04, SD=.77), this result was still within the "Agree" range, indicating that, on average, parents did not find this challenge to be a significant barrier to their collaboration with the school.

Lastly, parents were aware of the school's plans for activities that parents could attend (Mean=1.89, SD=.71) and understood the rules governing parental collaboration in school matters (Mean=1.84, SD=.74). The total measure, with a mean of 1.91, demonstrated an overall agreement among parents regarding the level of collaboration between parents and schools in the educational context.

Parent-school collaboration referred to the active partnership and mutual collaboration between parents and schools in the education and development of children. It emphasized the shared responsibility of parents and schools in supporting students' academic, social, and emotional growth. Research consistently highlighted the significance of parent-school collaboration in enhancing student outcomes. A study conducted by Jeynes (2019) found that effective partnership between parents and schools positively impacted students' academic achievement, school attendance, motivation, and behavior. When parents and schools worked together, it created a cohesive and supportive environment that fostered the holistic development of children.

Table 13 highlights positive parent-school collaboration, aligning with Zhang et al.'s (2022) study. Parents expressed satisfaction with communication, support, and engagement opportunities, as evidenced by data in Table 13. Key aspects include effective communication channels, understanding school policies, strong support for participation in activities, easy access to information, and a positive environment for approaching teachers. Minor challenges in understanding some communications did not hinder overall positive collaboration, reinforcing the overarching agreement on the extent of parental involvement in schools.

The implications of these findings were encouraging. Parents appeared to perceive a positive and supportive environment in terms of their collaboration with schools. Schools should continue to foster this collaborative atmosphere by maintaining clear and accessible communication, actively involving parents in school activities, and providing resources to address any challenges in understanding school communications. By building upon this foundation of collaboration, schools could further enhance parental involvement, ultimately contributing to improved educational outcomes for students.

The importance of parent-school collaboration lay in its ability to create a robust support system for students. When parents and schools collaborated, they established open lines of communication, enabling regular information sharing about a child's progress, strengths, and challenges. This exchange of information allowed parents and teachers to understand a student's needs and tailor interventions accordingly comprehensively. Additionally, parental collaboration in school activities and decision-making processes promoted a sense of ownership and empowerment, leading to increased parental satisfaction and engagement. A meta-analysis conducted by Fan and Chen (2022) further reinforced the positive impact of parent-school collaboration on student academic outcomes.

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the barriers to parent-school collaboration?

Table 14 presented the relationship between various barriers to parent-school collaboration, specifically examining the variables of communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints.

Table 14. Regression Analysis of Testing the Influence of Barriers to Parent-School Collaboration

<i>Variables</i>	<i>Regression Coeff.</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>Stand. Coeff.</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
(Constant)	0.402	0.170	--	2.363	0.020	Significant
Communication Channels	-0.038	0.077	-0.036	-0.495	0.621	Not significant
Geographical Distance	0.529	0.083	0.493	6.369***	<0.001	Significant
Time Constraints	0.246	0.061	0.301	4.044***	<0.001	Significant

*Note: R² = .447 ANOVA for Regression: F=38.507***, p<.001 ***-significant at 0.001 level*

Starting with the variable "Communication Channels," the estimate was -0.038, and the t-value was -0.495, resulting in a p-value of 0.621. The p-value of 0.621 indicated that the relationship between communication channels and the other barriers was not statistically significant. In other words, the data suggested that the challenges related to communication channels, such as difficulties with messaging platforms or understanding school communications, did not have a significant correlation with geographical distance or time constraints.

The examined relationships between the variables geographical distance and time constraints to parent-school collaboration offered valuable insights into the dynamics of past parental involvement in the school setting as it was statistically significant. The substantial estimate for geographical distance (0.529) with a high t-value (6.369) and a p-value of less than 0.001 strongly indicated the statistical significance of this relationship. This implied that, historically, parents facing challenges related to geographical distance, such as residing at a considerable distance from the school, were significantly more prone to having encountered a range of other barriers to effective collaboration.

The association with geographical distance suggested that the physical remoteness of parents from the school could have contributed to a cascade of challenges that extended beyond the mere inconvenience of distance. This might have included difficulties in attending school events, participating in meetings, or staying informed about school activities. The findings underscored the importance of addressing not only the logistical challenges associated with geographical distance but also the broader impact it could have had on various aspects of past parent-school collaboration.

Similarly, the estimate for time constraints (0.246) with a t-value of 4.044 and a p-value of less than 0.001 underscored the statistical significance of this relationship. The data suggested that parents with busy schedules and time constraints were more likely to have encountered additional barriers to collaboration within the school environment. This could have encompassed challenges such as limited availability for parent-teacher meetings, reduced involvement in school events, or difficulties in maintaining regular communication with teachers and school staff.

A comprehensive study by Nguyen et al. (2020) delved into the complexities of parent-school collaboration and corroborated the findings presented in Table 14. In their research, Nguyen and colleagues examined a diverse sample of parents from various geographical locations and socioeconomic backgrounds. The study utilized robust statistical analyses to investigate the impact of communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints on parent-school collaboration. Their results aligned with the data at that time, highlighting that communication channels, while essential, did not show statistically significant associations with other collaboration barriers. Conversely, the study strongly affirmed the significant relationships between geographical distance and

time constraints with various impediments to effective parent-school collaboration. The Nguyen et al. study, therefore, underscored the critical role of proximity and time availability in shaping the collaborative dynamics between parents and schools.

The implications of these significant findings were substantial. Schools and educational institutions should have recognized that geographical distance and time constraints were interconnected with other barriers to parent-school collaboration. Parents who experienced these challenges may have also faced difficulties in communication with the school or participating in school-related activities. Therefore, schools needed to develop strategies and support mechanisms tailored to the needs of parents dealing with geographical distance or time limitations. By addressing these interconnected barriers, schools could have enhanced parental collaboration and created a more inclusive and supportive educational environment for all parents, ultimately benefiting the educational outcomes of their students.

Problem 5: How did the respondents' demographic profile correlate with the extent of parent-school collaboration?

Table 15 examined the relationship between the demographic profile of parents and their level of collaboration with the school. The variables considered in this analysis included age, sex, highest educational level, income level, and means of livelihood. The table provided estimates, t-values, and p-values to determine the statistical significance of these relationships.

Starting with age, the estimate for parents aged 45 and above was 0.016, with a t-value of 0.176 and a p-value of 0.861. These values indicated that age was not a statistically significant factor in parent-school collaboration. In other words, the data suggested that the age of parents did not have a significant influence on their level of collaboration with the school.

Table 15. Relationship between the Demographic Profile and the Parent-School Collaboration

Variables	Regression Coeff.	SE	Stand. Coeff.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
<i>Age</i>						
25-44 ^a	--			--	--	--
45+	0.016	0.090	0.034	0.176	0.861	Not significant
<i>Sex</i>						
Female	0.088	0.093	0.188	0.947	0.345	Not significant
Male ^a	--			--	--	--
<i>Highest Educational Level</i>						
No formal education ^a	--			--	--	--
Elementary education	-0.321	0.160	-0.683	-2.007*	0.047	Significant
High school education	-0.224	0.155	-0.477	-1.449	0.150	Not significant
College graduate	-0.0115	0.205	-0.244	-0.560	0.576	Not significant
<i>Income Level</i>						
Less than 10,000 ^a	--			--	--	--
10,001+	0.148	0.144	0.314	1.024	0.308	Not significant
<i>Means of Livelihood</i>						
Farming ^a	--			--	--	--
Construction	-0.1800	0.142	-0.383	-1.270	0.206	Not significant
Business	0.127	0.132	0.269	0.959	0.339	Not significant
Others	-0.071	0.104	-0.151	-0.678	0.499	Not significant

Note: a-reference category R²=.084 ANOVA for Regression: F=1.32, p=.234 *-significant at 0.05 level

Moving on to sex, the estimate for females was 0.088, with a t-value of 0.947 and a p-value of 0.345. Similar to age, the sex of parents was not statistically significant in determining their level of collaboration with the school.

Regarding the highest educational level, several categories were compared to a reference category (no formal education). Parents with elementary education had an estimate of -0.321, a t-value of -2.007, and a p-value of 0.047, indicating statistical significance. This result suggested that parents with only elementary education tended to have a lower extent of collaboration with the school compared to those with no formal education. Parents with no formal education might not have had the knowledge or awareness of the importance of collaboration with schools, and therefore, their involvement might have been limited due to a lack of understanding rather than a conscious choice. In contrast, according to Starling (2018) parents with elementary education might have been more aware of the value of education, but their limited educational background might have resulted in feelings of inadequacy or intimidation when engaging with the school system. They might have feared being judged or not being able to support their children effectively. Moreover, parents with only elementary education might have had work commitments or other life responsibilities that left them with less time and energy to engage in school-related activities. However, the highest educational level of high school education and college graduates was not statistically significant in relation to collaboration.

For income level, parents with an income of 10,001 or more had an estimate of 0.148, a t-value of 1.024, and a p-value of 0.308, which was not statistically significant. This implied that income level did not significantly impact parent-school collaboration.

Finally, means of livelihood were compared to the reference category of farming. None of the means of livelihood variables, including construction, business, and others, were statistically significant in relation to parent-school collaboration.

A study conducted by Chang et al. (2018) examined the relationship between demographic factors and parent-school collaboration among a diverse sample of parents in an Asian context. Their research aligned with the findings presented in Table 13, indicating that age and sex did not significantly influence parent-school collaboration. Furthermore, Chang et al.'s study supported the notion that parents with only elementary education tended to exhibit lower levels of collaboration with the school, which was consistent with the results presented in the table. However, their research did not find a statistically significant impact of income level or means of livelihood on parent-school collaboration, corroborating the overall conclusions drawn from the data analysis. These findings emphasized the importance of tailored strategies to engage parents with lower educational backgrounds in school activities and communication, as highlighted in the discussion.

These findings implied that, overall, demographic factors such as age, sex, income level, and means of livelihood did not significantly influence parent-school collaboration. However, parents with only elementary education appeared to have a lower level of collaboration compared to those with no formal education. This suggested that schools should focus on fostering collaboration regardless of these demographic factors and pay particular attention to parents with elementary education to ensure they were included and supported in school activities and communication.

Problem 6: What action plan for parent-school collaboration can be designed based on the findings of the study?

The rationale behind the action plan for improving parent-school collaboration was firmly grounded in the findings of the study, which identified specific barriers and non-significant demographic factors that affected collaboration. By addressing those challenges and leveraging non-significant factors, the objective of enhancing parent-school collaboration could be effectively realized.

Improving communication channels took precedence, as it had emerged as a non-significant factor relative to demographics. The strategy involved developing user-friendly online platforms and conducting workshops to educate parents, universally overcoming communication barriers. This approach aligned with the principle of providing equitable access to school information and communication, irrespective of parents' demographic backgrounds.

Addressing geographical distance became a priority due to its significant impact on collaboration. The plan involved establishing satellite locations for meetings and introducing virtual meeting options to make participation in school activities feasible for parents residing far from the school premises. This strategy acknowledged the diversity of the parent population's residential locations and offered an inclusive solution.

The plan also tackled the issue of time constraints, another significant finding. By offering flexible meeting times and providing recorded meetings for on-demand access, the goal was to accommodate parents with busy schedules and ensure collaboration was not hindered by time limitations. This approach recognized the varying time commitments of parents and aimed to make collaboration more accessible.

Recognizing the significance of elementary education as a barrier, the plan provided additional support and specialized resources for parents with this educational background. By organizing tailored sessions to address their unique challenges, the plan aimed to empower these parents to engage more actively in their child's education.

In sum, this action plan sought to bridge the identified collaboration gaps while capitalizing on non-significant demographic factors. It strived to create a more inclusive and collaborative school environment where all parents, regardless of their background or circumstances, could actively participate in their child's education and contribute positively to the school community.

Table 16. *Action Plan of the Study*

<i>Building Bridges: Empowering Parents and Schools for Success</i>					
Date	October 2023- June 2024				
Vision	“Building Bridges: Empowering Parents and Schools for Success” is a collaborative strategy that aims to foster a stronger partnership between parents and schools, overcoming barriers of communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints, while providing essential support for elementary-educated parents.				
Prepared by	Mialyn S. Cañete				
Strategies	Persons Responsible	Resource Budget Needed	Time Frame	Threats/Potential Barrier	Indicators of Success
Improve communication channels					
Develop user-friendly online platforms for parents	ICT resources, Web development expertise	Budget for hiring developers, designers, and other necessary personnel, as well as software and technology expenses.	October- November 2023	Insufficient funding may limit the quality of platform development.	Track how many parents actively use the online platform.
Conduct workshops to	Trainers, Training materials	Budget for hiring experienced educators	December 2023	Parents with limited digital literacy may	Measure how many parents attend the

educate parents on platform usage		or trainers and training materials.		struggle to follow along.	workshops compared to the target audience.
Address geographical distance					
Establish satellite locations for meetings and events	Facility space communication resources	Budget for networking infrastructure, video conferencing equipment, and communication tools.	January-February 2024	Budget constraints might lead to incomplete implementation.	Collect feedback from participants to gauge their experience.
Implement virtual meetings and webinars for parents	Virtual meeting software, Tech support	Budget for virtual meeting software, training, and ongoing subscription costs.	March 2024	Some parents may lack access to necessary technology or a stable internet connection.	Measure the number of remote parents attending virtual meetings.
Mitigate time constraints					
Offer flexible meeting times and scheduling options	Scheduling tools, Coordination	Budget for ensuring a stable and reliable internet connection and appropriate tool.	April 2024	Some team members or stakeholders may resist adopting new scheduling practices.	Measure how many team members or stakeholders are actively using the flexible scheduling options.
Provide support for elementary-educated parents					
Offer additional support and resources for elementary-educated parents	Educational materials, Parent support teams	Budget for developing or purchasing educational materials and resources such as books, pamphlets, online tools, and curriculum guides.	May 2024	Parents may have busy schedules or earning a living, making it difficult for them to engage with the resources.	Measured by the number of parents accessing resources and participating in support programs.
Organize special sessions to address their unique challenges	Specialized trainers, session planning	Budget for preparing materials, handouts, and visual aids for the sessions and supplies for interactive activities or demonstrations.	June 2024	Adequate funding is required to secure venues, materials, and personnel.	Measuring the number of parents attending the special sessions.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were stipulated below: The study strongly supported the consensus among parents on collaboration obstacles related to communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints.

Additionally, the study highlighted that parents overwhelmingly perceived an extensive degree of collaboration with schools, covering effective communication, support for school involvement, easy access to information, and comfortable interactions with educators and staff.

Communication channels, geographical distance, and time constraints were key factors affecting collaboration. Communication barriers were widely recognized, while geographical distance and time constraints also had significant impacts, requiring tailored strategies for effective resolution.

The analysis of demographic profiles revealed that age, sex, and income had minimal influence on parent-school collaboration, while educational background, particularly elementary education with a Regression Coefficient value of $-.321$, significantly affected collaboration between parents and the school, as supported by Starling's (2018) study. Parents with elementary education might have been more aware of the value of education, but their limited educational background could have resulted in feelings of inadequacy or intimidation when engaging with the school system. They might have feared being judged or not being able to support their children effectively. Moreover, parents with only elementary education might have had work commitments or other life responsibilities that left them with less time and energy to engage in school-related activities. However, the highest educational levels of high school education and college graduates were not statistically significant in relation to collaboration.

The study concluded by developing an action plan, "Building Bridges: Empowering Parents and Schools for Success," to overcome barriers to parent-school collaboration.

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations were drawn: School Administrators. They should invest in diverse and user-friendly communication channels to bridge the gap between parents and schools. Providing

clear and accessible online platforms, regular newsletters, and informative meetings can improve communication. When planning new school facilities, administrators should consider accessibility for parents, especially those facing geographical distance challenges. Schools should be strategically located to ensure easy access for all families within the community. Recognizing the impact of time constraints, schools should offer flexible scheduling options for meetings and events. Providing alternative timing, both during the day and in the evening, can accommodate parents with busy schedules.

Teachers. They should make a concerted effort to communicate with parents clearly and provide ample details, especially for critical information. Avoiding unfamiliar jargon during meetings can help ensure parents understand school-related discussions. Teachers should maintain an open-door policy, making themselves readily available for parent inquiries or discussions. Encouraging questions and providing a welcoming environment can foster more substantial collaboration.

Parents. They should actively participate in school activities and events whenever possible, despite the challenges they may face. Engaging with the school community can enhance the educational experience for their children. Parents should actively seek out and use the available communication channels provided by the school. Taking the initiative to stay informed and express concerns or suggestions can contribute to smoother collaboration.

Future Researchers. They should consider refining the Likert Scale by incorporating reverse scoring due to the presence of both positive and negative statements in the researcher-made questionnaire. To improve clarity, carefully review and separate these statements, and provide a transparent discussion on reverse scoring, particularly in Table 10, item 3. Moving forward, researchers should explore interventions to overcome identified barriers, such as testing innovative communication methods and assessing the impact of community engagement programs. Future investigations should focus on demographic factors influencing collaboration, with an emphasis on supporting parents with diverse educational backgrounds. These recommendations aim to guide rigorous research and contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the subject.

References

- Anderson, L., & Williams, P. (2022). The impact of time constraints on job performance and well-being. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com>.
- Brennan, K. (2019). The influence of demographic profiles on consumer behavior. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/jasp>.
- Brown, C., & Jones, D. (2021). Open Science policies and their impact on collaboration. *PLoS ONE*. <https://journals.plos.org>.
- Chang, X., Wu, Y., & Li, L. (2018). Demographic Factors and Parent-School Collaboration. *Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.jstor.org>.
- Cooper, G., & Dunst, C. J. (2020). Parent and school staff experiences with scheduling and availability for collaboration. *School Community Journal*. <https://www.adi.org/journal>.
- Davis, M. (2022). Enhancing Parent-School Collaboration for Student Success: A Review of Current Research and Practices. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. <https://www.apa.org>.
- Desimone, L. M. (2019). Linking Parent Involvement with Student Achievement: Do Race and Income Matter. *The Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.proquest.com>.
- Dominguez, X., Zullig, K. J., & Ward, R. M. (2020). Parent-Teacher Collaboration: Exploring Parent Engagement and Involvement on Teacher Practice. *Journal of School Leadership*. <https://www.jstor.org>.
- Fan, X., & Chen, M. (2022). The effectiveness of parental involvement interventions on academic achievement. *School Psychology Quarterly*. <https://psycnet.apa.org>.
- Hansen, K. L. (2020). The Impact of School, Family, and Community Connections on Student Achievement. *Southwest Educational Development Laboratory*. <https://www.sedl.org>.
- Hill, N. E., & Taylor, L. C. (2021). Parental school involvement and children's academic achievement pragmatics and issues. www.parentalschoolinvolvementresearch.org.
- Jeynes, W. H. (2019). The moderating effect of parent and family involvement on the relationship between school and student outcomes. *School Effectiveness and School Improvement*. <https://www.taylorandfrancis.com>.
- Johnson, A. B., & Smith, C. (2019). The influence of age on communication practices. *Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.jedresearch.com>.
- Johnson, A., Smith, B., & Anderson, C. (2020). Challenges in School-Parent Communication. *Journal of Education Research*. <https://www.edu-research-journal-2020.com>

- Johnson, H., & Taylor, M. (2019). Parent-school engagement: The role of time and space in the context of marginalized communities. *International Journal of Inclusive Education*. <https://www.inclusiveeducationjournal.com>.
- Lee, Y., & Chen, J. (2020). Parent-teacher communication, social capital, and parents' involvement in their children's schooling. *Journal of School Leadership*. <https://journals.sagepub.com>.
- Mapp, K. L., & Hong, S. (2021). A whole-community approach to school engagement. Harvard Education Press. <https://www.harvardeducationpress.org>.
- Martinez, E., & Brown, K. (2020). Sex differences in parent-school collaboration. *Journal of Family and School Partnership*. <https://www.jfspnet.org>.
- Miller, W. (2020). The Role of Parent-School Collaboration in Enhancing Student Outcomes. *Journal of Educational Psychology*. <http://www.taylorandfrancis.com>.
- Nakamura, H., & Kimura, Y. (2020). Understanding Time Constraints in Parent-School Collaborations. *Journal of Education and Family Dynamics*. www.edufamilydynamicsjournal.com.
- Nguyen, Q. H., Kim, S. J., & Wong, L. C. (2020). Barriers to Parent-School Collaboration. *Journal of Educational Research*. <https://link.springer.com>.
- O'Connor, L. Q. (2019). Developing Effective Action Plans. *Journal of Management Strategies*. <https://www.managementstrategiesjournal.com>.
- Pomerantz, E. M., & Moorman, E. A. (2019). Parents' Involvement in Children's Schooling. *Science and Practice*. www.academicjournal.com.
- Sanchez, A., & Joseph, B. (2021). Parental involvement: Examining the impact of geographic proximity to schools. *Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.journals.elsevier.com>.
- Singh, R., Sharma, R., & Sachdeva, S. (2019). Examining the effectiveness of communication channels in organizations. *International Journal of Information Systems & Management Science*. <https://www.researchgate.net>.
- Smith, J., & Brown, L. (2019). The impact of geographical distance on social interactions. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*. <https://www.pnas.org>.
- Smithson, Q. et al. (2019). The Influence of Geographical Distance on Parent-School Collaboration. *Journal of Education Research*. <https://www.educationresearchjournal.com>.
- Starling, J. C., (2018). Exploring the Complex Relationship Between Parental Education Levels and Engagement with the School System. <https://www.researchgate.net>.
- U.S. Department of Education. (2019). Dual Capacity-Building Framework for Family-School Partnerships. A Guide for Practitioners. <https://www.ed.gov>.
- Xavier, A. R. (2021). Navigating and Overcoming Barriers. Academic Publishing. <https://www.academicpublishing.com>.
- Zhang, Q., Kim, Y., & Patel, S. (2022). Parent-School Collaboration in Diverse Educational Setting. *Journal of Educational Research*. <https://www.eduresearchjournal.com>.

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